

[Introduction & Consent]

Dear reader,

Thank you for your interest in our survey, which is being conducted by Wageningen University in cooperation with the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment and the Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety, the Swedish National Veterinary Institute, and the Finnish Food Authority, as part of the EFSA partnering-grant project *ENhanced COMmunication in Risk Analysis (ENCOMRAN)*.

This survey deals with the communication between *risk assessors and risk managers* during the risk analysis process on national level in all EU member states. In this study, we define **risk assessment** as the scientifically based process of reviewing data and studies in order to evaluate food and feed risks associated with certain hazards. It involves steps such as hazard identification, hazard characterization, exposure assessment and risk characterization.

Risk management, is defined as the process of weighing policy alternatives and, if required, selecting the appropriate actions necessary to prevent, reduce or eliminate food and feed risks identified by risk assessment. It includes the planning, implementation and evaluation of any resulting actions taken to protect consumers, animals and the environment.

Both risk assessment and risk management are part of the **risk analysis** process, which spans from assessing hazards over risk communication up to the management of identified risks.

The *ENCOMRAN* project aims to develop guidelines to improve the communication between risk managers and risk assessors. For this reason, we would like to gather information from individuals who are actively involved in risk assessment and/or risk management on a **working level**. If you feel that this does not apply to you or your work, we would kindly ask you to forward this link to colleagues who might fit these criteria.

The main part of the survey will be divided into different blocks, each dealing with different aspects of the risk analysis process: its general characteristics, its preparation, the communication in the work process and some reflections on how well you perceive those processes to work. To make things easier, these sections will focus only on the last risk analysis in which you were involved. Additionally, in a shorter part of the survey, we will ask you a few questions on how you think the communication between risk assessors and risk managers can be improved during risk analysis. To help us in our analysis, the questionnaire will start and finish with a few background questions on your work and demographics.

The questionnaire is anonymous and does not contain any questions that could easily identify you. The data collected will be treated confidentially. It will only be passed on or published in anonymized form. Subgroups formed on the basis of variables such as organizational structure will only be analysed separately if they contain at least five individuals.

You can find further information on how your data is protected at:

<https://www.wur.nl/en/show/Policy-document-for-processing-personal-data-WUR.htm>

There are no right or wrong answers in the survey – we are only interested in ***your personal thoughts, feelings, and experiences*** within the risk analysis process. If you feel that you cannot answer a question or that a question does not apply to you, you can use the “I don’t know / I prefer not to say” option.

It will take you about 30 to 40 minutes to complete the questionnaire. If you want to break from filling out the questionnaire and finish it later, you will need to access the link via the same computer and the same browser to resume at the point where you left. To pause while filling out the questionnaire, you can simply close the tab or window in your browser.

Your participation in the study is **voluntary**. If you want to stop participating in the survey, you can do this by simply closing the window in your browser. You can stop at any time and without giving a reason.

If you have any questions about this project, please contact the project coordinator, Gunnar Andersson (gunnar.andersson@sva.se).

By clicking the option "**I consent**" below, you agree to participate in this research; you confirm that you understand the information provided above and that you agree to the stated conditions for participating in this survey; you confirm that you understand that participation in the survey is voluntary and that you can stop participating at any time without giving a reason; and you confirm that you understand the data processing information and agree to the stated conditions of data processing.

- Yes, I consent (1)
- No, I do not consent (0)

Screen-Out-Message [To be displayed if a participant selects “No, I do not consent”]

Thank you for taking the time to consider participating in this survey. You can now exit the survey by closing this window.

[ALL] BACKGROUND QUESTIONS I

BG1 How would you describe your work within the risk analysis process? [SC]

Please note: The answer to this question is crucial for the remainder of the questionnaire, as it determines the questions that will be displayed for you. If you select "I don't know/I prefer not to say", you will not be able to continue with the survey.

I work...

- ... only in risk assessment. (1)
- ... both in risk assessment and in risk management. (2)
- ... only in risk management. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

Screen-Out-Message [To be displayed if someone selects "I don't know / I prefer not to say"]
"Thank you for taking the time to consider participating in this survey. You can now exit the survey by closing this window."

BG2a [3C-Desi] Which parts of the risk analysis process is the **organization** for which you work involved in? [SC]

My organization...

- ... only provides risk assessment. (1)
- ... provides both risk assessment and risk management. (2)
- ... only provides risk management. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

Filter: IF BG2a = 2

BG2b [3C-Desi] How is the risk analysis process structured within your organization? [SC]

In my organization, risk assessment and risk management are usually handled...

- ... by different persons working in different departments. (1)
- ... by different persons within the same department. (2)
- ... by the same person. (3)
- ... in another way (please specify): _____ (88)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

BG3a [3C-Desi] Is there a person or entity who coordinates your interaction with your risk analysis counterpart? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

Filter: IF BG3a = 1

BG3b [3C-Desi] What type of entity coordinates the risk analysis?

Please specify below

FILTER for all [RA]-blocks (= RALG1 to RALR9b): BG1 = 1

[RA] GENERAL QUESTIONS ON LAST RISK ANALYSIS

[Introduction]

To get a better understanding of the communication between people working in risk assessment and risk management, we would like to take a closer look at specific details within the risk analysis process. For this, we would like you to think about the **last risk analysis you were involved in and that you provided a risk assessment for**. It should fulfil the following two criteria: 1) The assessment was requested by risk management via a mandate; i.e., via an official order or commission to perform a risk assessment. 2) The risk assessment has already been submitted to risk management and has been consulted for risk management purposes. Please answer **all following questions** with this particular risk analysis in mind.

In this first part of the questionnaire, we have a few general questions about your last risk analysis:

RALG1 [Subject area] Within which subject area did you prepare this last risk assessment? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

- Biological hazards in food. (1)
- Chemical hazards in food. (2)
- Physical hazards in food. (3)
- Biological hazards in drinking water. (4)
- Chemical hazards in drinking water. (5)
- Biological hazards in feed. (6)
- Chemical hazards in feed. (7)
- Physical hazards in feed. (8)
- Biological hazards in water to animals. (9)
- Chemical hazards in water to animals. (10)
- Emerging risks (related to food or feed). (11)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not so say. (99)

RALG2 [Routine vs. incident] Which of the following categories did your last risk assessment fall into? [SC]

- Routine risk assessment, i.e., a systematic review of all available scientific data to evaluate the magnitude of risks associated with certain hazards. (1)
- Rapid risk assessment, i.e., a risk assessment based on limited data due to time constraints (often used in initial stages of an event or after an incident of potential public health concern). (2)
- Expert opinion, i.e., a summary of evidence-based views given by experts in the field (often used when there is a lack of data). (3)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALG3 [Length of risk assessment] How long did the last risk assessment take? [SC]

- Less than a month. (1)
- One to three months. (2)
- Four to six months. (3)
- Seven to twelve months. (4)
- More than a year. (5)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALG4 [Tasks and topics of work] Which tasks were you involved in during your last risk analysis? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

		Code/ Filter [multiple choice]
Screening and early warning.	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Problem framing.	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Determining how to assess the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Formulation of the mandate (i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment).	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Hazard identification.	<input type="checkbox"/>	5
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	6
Hazard characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	7
Risk characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	8
Gathering and assessing risk perceptions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	9
Gathering and assessing social concerns.	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
Compiling risk profiles.	<input type="checkbox"/>	12
Knowledge characterization (e.g. in terms of uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity).	<input type="checkbox"/>	13
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	14
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	15
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	16
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	17

Planning options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	18
Implementing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	19
Controlling the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	20
Evaluating the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	21
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
Risk communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>	23
Stakeholder engagement.	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

RALG5 [Organizational structure] Including yourself, how many people were involved in your last risk assessment?

If you don't know the exact number, please enter your best estimate.

_____ people

[@Joao: please program the text field so that the participants can only enter **numbers**, not letters.]

RALG6 [3C Key personnel] Which of the following scenarios best describes your interaction with risk management during the last risk analysis? [SC, R]

- I interacted directly with risk management on a working level, supervisory staff was only involved during approval processes. (1)
- A coordinating entity facilitated my interaction with risk management. (2)
- Me, supervisory staff and potential colleagues interacted on equal footing with risk management. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

RALG7 [3C Organizational autonomy] During the last risk analysis, to what extent did you work autonomously from risk management? [SC, R]

- The risk assessment was performed fully autonomously. (1)
- A coordinating entity from my own organization coordinated the risk analysis process. (2)
- A coordinating entity from another organization coordinated the risk analysis process. (3)
- I worked jointly with risk management. (4)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

RALG8a [3C Resource allocation] During the last risk analysis, did you share any resources (i.e., budget, personnel, facilities...) with risk management? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALG8a = 1

RALG8b [3C Resource allocation] What resources did you share with risk management?

Please specify below:

[RA] PREPERATION OF THE RISK ANALYSIS

With the next questions, we want to learn more about how your last risk analysis as specified above got started:

RALP1 [Formulation of mandate] How was the last risk assessment mandate formulated? The term “mandate” describes the official order or commission you received to perform the risk assessment. [SC]

- It was formulated by risk management alone. (1)
- It was formulated mainly by risk management, but with some input from risk assessment. (2)
- Risk assessment and risk management formulated the risk assessment mandate in a joint process. (3)
- In another way (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALP2 [Formulation of mandate] What kind of information was included in the last risk assessment mandate?

Please tick all that apply.

- A description of the risk to be assessed. (1)
- The intended use of the risk assessment. (2)
- Information on different risk management strategies pertaining to this risk. (3)
- A description of the circumstance that gave rise to the enquiry. (4)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALP3a [MCDA] Did the last risk assessment mandate define the decision factors and criteria that would be used to compare different management options (for example specifications made for a multi criteria decision analysis, short MCDA)? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALP3a = 1

RALP3b [MCDA] What decision factors and criteria were these?

Please specify below:

FILTER IF RALP3a = 1

RALP3c [MCDA] To what extent were these decision factors and criteria useful or not useful in facilitating the interaction with risk management? [SC]

Not at all useful 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very useful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

FILTER IF RALP3a = 1

RALP3d [MCDA] To what extent did these decision factors and criteria influence your last risk assessment? [SC, R – Except (3) & (99)]

- They influenced how the risk assessment was conducted. (1)
- They influenced how the results of the risk assessment were presented. (2)
- They did not influence the risk assessment. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALP4 [Comprehensibility / common ground] How would you rate the comprehensibility of the last risk assessment mandate? [R]

If you saw several versions of the mandate (e.g., an earlier draft and the official version), please answer the question only in relation to the final version of the mandate.

	Do not agree at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Agree completely 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
The risk assessment mandate was written in an understandable way. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The mandate defined the risk to be assessed precisely and clearly. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The mandate clearly stated the purpose for which the assessment was needed. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had problems understanding what exactly was expected from my risk assessment. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had difficulties understanding some of the technical terms used in the risk assessment mandate. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[RA] EXECUTION OF THE RISK ANALYSIS

In this part of the questionnaire, we would like you to focus on the interaction with risk management while working on the last risk analysis.

RALE1 [3C Decision making] Who made the decisions regarding the risk assessment methodology during the last risk analysis? [SC]

- Risk assessment alone (1)
- Risk management alone (2)
- A coordinating entity (3)
- Risk assessment and risk management collectively (4)
- Other (please specify): (88)_____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALE2a [3C-TURF] Did you experience conflicts regarding responsibilities and decision making power between risk assessment and risk management during the last risk analysis? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALE2a = 1

RALE2b [3C-TURF] How did you mainly deal with these conflicts? [SC, R]

- We did not address the conflicts. (1)
- We resolved the conflicts with help of a third party. (2)
- We resolved the conflicts in a team effort without the involvement of a third party. (3)
- Other (please specify): (88)_____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALE2b = 2, 3

RALE2c [Conflict resolution] How did you resolve these conflicts?

Please specify below:

RALE3a [3C Info; Frequency of communication] How often did you communicate with risk management while working on the last risk analysis?

Never

Constantly

<input type="radio"/> I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

FILTER IF RALE3a < 50 %

RALE3b [Motivations for non-communication] Why did you rarely communicate with risk management while working on the last risk analysis?

[MC, R]

Please tick all that apply.

- Limited time. (1)
- Ensuring the independence of the risk assessment. (2)
- No trustful relationship with the risk manager (3)
- Organizational constraints. (4)
- Risk manager unwilling to communicate. (5)
- Hierarchical constraints. (6)
- Other (please specify) (88): _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALE3a > 10 %

RALE3c [Motivations for communication] When you did communicate with risk management while working on the last risk analysis, what were the reasons? [MC, R]

Please tick all that apply.

- Clarification of the questions in the mandate from risk assessment. (1)
- Requesting additional information on the risk assessment mandate. (2)
- Giving further advice (e.g. management strategy). (3)
- Questions on the progress of the risk assessment. (4)
- Questions about the time schedule. (5)
- Keeping each other up to date. (6)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALE4 [Frequency-RiskGov] How frequently did you interact with risk management on the different topics in which you were involved?

[@Joao: Here we only want to display the items the participants ticked in RALG4 → please add a corresponding Filter]

	Never 1	Rarely 2	Sometimes 3	Often 4	Always 5	I don't know / I prefer not to say 99
Screening and early warning.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Problem framing.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Determining how to assess the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Formulation of the mandate (i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Hazard identification.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Hazard characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Risk characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gathering and assessing risk perceptions.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gathering and assessing social concerns.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Compiling risk profiles.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Knowledge characterization (e.g. in terms of uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Planning options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Implementing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Controlling the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Evaluating the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Risk communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

RALE5 [3C Information sharing] Besides the official mandate and the delivery of the risk assessment report, how would you characterize your communication with risk management? [MC, R]

- We communicated only if needed (e.g., additional questions) on a spontaneous basis. (1)
- We had formal proceedings for further information exchange (e.g., regular meetings). (2)
- We communicated openly and frequently. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALE6 [Mode of information sharing] How often did you use the following communication channels to communicate with risk management?

	Never (1)	Rarely (2)	Sometimes (3)	Often (4)	Always (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Official letter. (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
E-mail. (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Telephone. (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Video conference. (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Face-to-face conversation. (5)	<input type="radio"/>					
Chat and messenger service. (6)	<input type="radio"/>					

RALE7 [Effectiveness of communication channels, common ground] How effective were the following channels for your communication with risk management?

	Not at all effective 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very effective 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Official letter. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E-mail. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Telephone. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Video conference. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Face-to-face conversation. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Chat and messenger service. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RALE8a [3C System thinking] Did you use shared risk analysis information systems (e.g., databases or knowledge platforms) with risk management? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

FILTER IF RALE8a = 1

RALE8b [3C System thinking] Which role did these shared information systems play? [SC, R]

- They were only used if they facilitated the risk assessment. (1)
- They were used to facilitate the overall risk analysis process. (2)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALE9a [3C-FormI; guidelines for risk analysis process] To what extent was your interaction with risk management formalized?[R]

	Yes	No
There were informal (e.g. verbal) agreements on how our communication with risk management should proceed (e.g., in terms of roles and responsibilities). (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were specific formal guidelines for our communication with risk management (e.g., in terms of roles and responsibilities). (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)	<input type="radio"/>	

FILTER IF RALE9a Item 1 = Yes

RALE9b [3C-FormI] Who set these informal agreements? [SC]

- The agreements were set by either risk assessment or risk management. (1)
- The agreements were set by a coordinating entity. (2)
- The agreements were set jointly. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALE9a Item 1 = Yes

RALE9c [3C-FormI] Were these informal agreements rather restrictive or rather helpful for your communication?

Rather restrictive 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Rather helpful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

FILTER IF RALE9a Item 2 = Yes

RALE9d [3C-FormI] Who set these specific formal guidelines? [SC]

- The guidelines were set by either risk assessment or risk management. (1)
- The guidelines were set by a coordinating entity. (2)
- The guidelines were set jointly. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALE9a Item 2 = Yes

RALE9e [FormI] Were these specific formal guidelines rather restrictive or rather helpful for your communication?

Rather restrictive 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Rather helpful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RALE10a [Informal communication] During the last risk analysis, did you have informal communication with risk management?

The term "informal communication" refers to all communication between risk assessors and risk managers that takes place outside of the predetermined processes in risk analysis (e.g., a spontaneous phone call to clarify upcoming questions).

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

FILTER IF RALE10a = 1

RALE10b [Importance of informal communication] What impact did informal communication have during the last risk analysis? [R]

	Do not agree at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Agree completely 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Informal communication facilitated open communication between risk assessment and risk management. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication improved understanding of the mandate to the risk assessor. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication impaired the independence of the risk assessment process. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication improved the comprehensibility of the risk assessment. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication facilitated handing over the risk assessment to risk management. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication increased trust between risk assessment and risk management. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RALE11 [Independence] To what extent did your communication with risk management influence the **results** of the last risk assessment?

Not at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very strongly 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
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○ ○ ○ ○ ○ | ○

RALE12 [Independence] To what extent did your communication with risk management influence how the results from the last risk assessment were **presented** in the risk assessment report?

not at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very strongly 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
○	○	○	○	○	○

RALE13 [Mutual needs] Which of the following aspects did your final risk assessment report cover? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

- The results of the risk assessment. (1)
- Risk benefit analysis (2)
- Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate. (3)
- Uncertainties in the risk assessment. (4)
- Other limitations of the risk assessment. (5)
- Background information. (6)
- Raw data. (7)
- Details on the methodology. (8)
- Details on the impact of different management scenarios. (9)
- Recommendations for management decisions. (10)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

[RA] REFLECTION ON THE RISK ANALYSIS

In this part of the questionnaire, we would like you to take a step back and reflect on the last risk analysis in which you were involved as a whole.

RALR1 [Quality of risk analysis process] How would you generally rate the quality of the following aspects within the last risk analysis? [R]

	Very poor 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very good 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Work process. (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Transparency amongst all involved partners. (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Meeting risk analysis goals (effectiveness). (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Minimizing resource requirements (efficiency). (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Openness with risk management. (5)	<input type="radio"/>					
Flexibility. (6)	<input type="radio"/>					
Time management. (7)	<input type="radio"/>					
Timeliness. (8)	<input type="radio"/>					

RALR2 [Satisfaction, dependent variable] How satisfied were you overall with the communication between you and the risk manager during the last risk analysis?

Not at all satisfied 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very satisfied 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RALR3a [Proximity, common Ground] Had you worked previously with the particular risk manager? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALR3a = 1

RALR3b [Proximity / mutual needs] How important was it for your work in the last risk analysis that you already knew the risk manager for whom you were conducting the assessment?

Not at all important 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very important 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RALR4 [Trust] How would you describe your relationship with the risk manager in the last risk analysis? [R]

	Do not agree at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Agree completely 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
We did not get to know each other personally while working on the risk analysis. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable about asking them all kinds of clarifying questions. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable about bringing up problems and challenges. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable about asking them for help. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt that my skills and expertise were valued by them. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trusted their abilities regarding the risk analysis process. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trusted them to work in line with my own interests. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RALR5 [3C-Trust] Which role did trust play for the success of the last risk analysis? [SC, R]

- It was not necessary that risk assessors and risk managers trusted each other. (1)
- Trust was only necessary between supervisory staff of risk assessment and risk management, not on a working level. (2)

- It was crucial that all partners trusted each other. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALR6a [Mutual needs / common ground] Did you receive any feedback on your last risk assessment from risk management? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALR6a = 1

RALR6b [Common Ground] How useful was the feedback for preparation of future risk assessments?

Not at all helpful 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very helpful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RALR7 [Mutual needs] On which aspects of your last risk assessment would you have liked to receive some (additional) feedback? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

- The results of the risk assessment. (1)
- Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate. (2)
- Uncertainties in the risk assessment. (3)
- Other limitations of the risk assessment. (4)
- Background information. (5)
- Raw data. (6)
- Details on the methodology. (7)
- Recommendations for management strategies. (8)
- Details on the impact of different management scenarios. (9)
- Impact of the risk assessment on risk management. (10)
- Usability of the risk assessment report in risk management. (11)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALR8 [Mutual needs / common ground] Did the risk management tell you how they plan to use or used the results of your last risk assessment in the risk management process? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RALR9a [Information sharing] During the last risk analysis, did you feel any constraints in your communication with risk management? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RALR9a = 1

RALR9b [Information sharing] What kind of constraints were they?

Please specify below.

FILTER for [RM]-Blocks (= RMLG1 to RMLR7b): IF BG1 = 3

[RM] GENERAL QUESTIONS ON LAST RISK ANALYSIS

[Introduction]

To get a better understanding of the communication between people working in risk assessment and risk management, we would like to take a closer look at specific details within the risk analysis process. For this, we would like you to think about the **last risk analysis you were involved in and that you received a risk assessment for**. It should fulfil the following two criteria: 1) The risk assessment was requested by risk management via an official mandate; i.e., via an official order or commission to perform a risk assessment. 2) The risk assessment has already been submitted to risk management and has been consulted for risk management purposes. Please answer **all following questions** with this particular risk analysis in mind.

In this first part of the questionnaire, we have a few general questions about your last risk analysis:

- RMLG1 [subject area] Within which subject area did you formulate the last risk assessment mandate? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

- Biological hazards in food. (1)
- Chemical hazards in food. (2)
- Physical hazards in food. (3)
- Biological hazards in drinking water. (4)
- Chemical hazards in drinking water. (5)
- Biological hazards in feed. (6)
- Chemical hazards in feed. (7)
- Physical hazards in feed. (8)
- Biological hazards in water to animals. (9)
- Chemical hazards in water to animals. (10)
- Emerging risks (related to food or feed). (11)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not so say. (99)

RMLG2 [Routine vs. incident] Which of the following categories did this last risk assessment fall into? [SC]

- Routine risk assessment, i.e., a systematic review of all available scientific data to evaluate the magnitude of risks associated with certain hazards. (1)
- Rapid risk assessment, i.e., a risk assessment based on limited data due to time constraints (often used in initial stages of an event or after an incident of potential public health concern). (2)
- Expert opinion, i.e., a summary of evidence-based views given by experts in the field (often used when there is a lack of data). (3)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLG3 [Length of risk management] How long did the last risk management process take? [SC]

- Less than a month. (1)
- One to three months. (2)
- Four to six months. (3)
- Seven to twelve months. (4)
- More than a year. (5)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLG4 [Tasks and topics of work] Which tasks were you involved in during your last risk analysis? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

		Code/ Filter [multiple choice]
Screening and early warning.	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Problem framing.	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Determining how to assess the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Formulation of the mandate (i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment).	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Hazard identification.	<input type="checkbox"/>	5
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	6
Hazard characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	7
Risk characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	8
Gathering and assessing risk perceptions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	9
Gathering and assessing social concerns.	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
Compiling risk profiles.	<input type="checkbox"/>	12
Knowledge characterization (e.g. in terms of uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity).	<input type="checkbox"/>	13
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	14
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	15

Assessing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	16
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	17
Planning options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	18
Implementing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	19
Controlling the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	20
Evaluating the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	21
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
Risk communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>	23
Stakeholder engagement.	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

RMLG5 [Organizational structure] Including yourself, how many people were involved in the last risk management?

If you don't know the exact number, please enter your best estimate.

_____ people

[@Joao: please program the text field so that the participants can only enter **numbers**, not letters.]

RMLG6 [3C Key personnel] Which of the following scenarios best describes your interaction with risk assessment during the last risk analysis? [SC, R]

- I interacted directly with risk assessment on a working level, supervisory staff was only involved during approval processes. (1)
- A coordinating entity facilitated my interaction with risk assessment. (2)
- Me, supervisory staff and potential colleagues interacted on equal footing with risk assessment. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

RMLG7 [3C Organizational autonomy] During the last risk analysis, to what extent did you work autonomously from risk assessment? [SC, R]

- The risk management was performed fully autonomously. (1)
- A coordinating entity from my own organization coordinated the risk analysis process. (2)
- A coordinating entity from another organization coordinated the risk analysis process. (3)
- I worked jointly with the risk assessment. (4)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

RMLG8a [3C Resource allocation] During the last risk analysis, did you share any resources (i.e., budget, personnel, facilities...) with risk assessment? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLG8a = 1

RMLG8b [3C Resource allocation] What resources did you share with risk assessment?

Please specify below:

[RM] PREPERATION OF THE RISK ANALYSIS

With the next questions, we want to learn more about how your last risk analysis as specified above got started:

RMLP1 [Formulation of mandate] How was the last risk assessment mandate formulated? The term “mandate” describes the official order or commission you have sent out to perform the risk assessment. [SC]

- It was formulated by risk management alone. (1)
- It was formulated mainly by risk management, but with some input from risk assessment. (2)
- Risk assessment and risk management formulated the risk assessment mandate in a joint process. (3)
- In another way (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLP2 [Formulation of mandate] What kind of information did you include in the last risk assessment mandate?

Please tick all that apply.

- A description of the risk to be assessed. (1)
- The intended use of the risk assessment. (2)
- Information on different risk management strategies pertaining to this risk. (3)
- A description of the circumstance that gave rise to the enquiry. (4)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLP3a [MCDA] Did your last risk assessment mandate define the decision factors and criteria that would be used to compare different management options (for example specifications made for a multi criteria decision analysis, short MCDA)? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLP3a = 1

RMLP3b [MCDA] What decision factors and criteria were these?

Please specify below.

FILTER IF RMLP3a = 1

RMLP3c [MCDA] To what extent were these decision factors and criteria useful or not useful in facilitating the interaction with risk assessment? [SC]

Not at all useful 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very useful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLP4a [Mutual needs / common ground] Did you receive any feedback on the comprehensibility or any ambiguities of your last risk assessment mandate from risk assessment? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLP4a = 1

RMLP4b [Common ground] How useful was the feedback for preparation of future risk assessment mandates?

Not at all helpful 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very helpful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[RM] EXECUTION OF THE RISK ANALYSIS

In this part of the questionnaire, we would like you to focus on the interaction with risk assessment while working on the risk analysis.

RMLE1 [3C Decision making] Who made the decisions regarding management strategies during the last risk analysis? [R]

- Risk assessment alone (1)
- Risk management alone (2)
- A coordinating entity (3)
- Risk assessment and risk management collectively (4)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLE2a [3C-TURF] Did you experience conflicts regarding responsibilities and decision making power between risk assessment and risk management during the last risk analysis? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLE2a = 1

RMLE2b [3C-TURF] How did you mainly deal with these conflicts? [SC, R]

- We did not address the conflicts. (1)
- We resolved the conflicts with help of a third party. (2)
- We resolved the conflicts in a team effort without the involvement of a third party. (3)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLE2b = 2,3

RMLE2c [Conflict resolution] How did you resolve these conflicts?

Please specify below:

RMLE3a [3C Info; Frequency of communication] How often did you communicate with risk assessment during the last risk analysis process?

Never

Constantly

FILTER IF RMLE3a < 50 %

RMLE3b [Motivations for non-communication] Why did you rarely communicate with risk assessment during the last risk analysis? [MC, R]

Please tick all that apply.

- Limited time. (1)
- Ensuring the independence of the risk assessment. (2)
- No trustful relationship with the risk manager (3)
- Organizational constraints. (4)
- Risk manager unwilling to communicate. (5)
- Hierarchical constraints. (6)
- Other (please specify) (88): _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLE3a > 10 %

RMLE3c [Motivations for communication] When you did communicate with risk assessment while working on the last risk analysis, what were the reasons? [MC, R]

Please tick all that apply.

- Clarification of questions on the assignment by the risk manager. (1)
- Giving additional information on the risk assessment mandate. (2)
- Receiving further advice (e.g. management strategy). (3)
- Questions on the progress of the risk assessment. (4)
- Questions about the time schedule. (5)
- Keeping each other up to date. (6)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLE4 [Frequency-RiskGov] How frequently did you interact with risk assessment on the different topics you were involved in?

[@Joao: Here we only want to display the items the participants ticked in RMLG4 → please add a corresponding Filter]

	Never 1	Rarely 2	Sometime 3	Often 4	Always 5	I don't know / I prefer not to say 99
Screening and early warning.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Problem framing.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Determining how to assess the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Formulation of the mandate (i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Hazard identification.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Hazard characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Risk characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gathering and assessing risk perceptions.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gathering and assessing social concerns.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Compiling risk profiles.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Knowledge characterization (e.g. in terms of uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Planning options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Implementing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Controlling the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Evaluating the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Risk communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

RMLE5 [3C Information sharing] Besides the official mandate and the delivery of the risk assessment report, how would you characterize your communication with risk assessment? [MC, R]

- We communicated only if needed (e.g., additional questions) on a spontaneous basis. (1)
- We had formal proceedings for further information exchange (e.g., regular meetings). (2)
- We communicated openly and frequently. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLE6 [Mode of information sharing] How often did you use the following communication channels to communicate with risk assessment?

	Never (1)	Rarely (2)	Sometimes (3)	Often (4)	Always (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Official letter. (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
E-mail. (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Telephone. (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Video conference. (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Face-to-face conversation. (5)	<input type="radio"/>					
Chat and messenger service. (6)	<input type="radio"/>					

RMLE7 [Effectiveness of communication channels, common ground] How effective were the following channels for your communication with risk assessment?

	Not at all effective 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very effective 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Official letter. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E-mail. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Telephone. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Video conference. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Face-to-face conversation. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Chat and messenger service. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLE8a [3C-System thinking] Did you use shared risk analysis information systems (e.g., databases or knowledge platforms) with risk assessment? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say(99)

FILTER IF RMLE8a = 1

RMLE8b [3C-System thinking] Which role did these information systems play? [SC, R]

- They are only used if they facilitate the risk management. (1)
- They are used to facilitate the overall risk analysis process. (2)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLE9a [3C-Forml; guidelines for risk analysis process] To what extent was your interaction with risk assessment formalised? [R]

	Yes	No
There were informal (e.g., verbal) agreements on how our communication with risk assessment should proceed. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
There were specific formal guidelines for our communication with risk assessment. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)	<input type="radio"/>	

FILTER IF RMLE9a Item 1 = Yes

RMLE9b [3C-Forml] Who set these informal agreements? [SC]

- The agreements were set by either risk assessment or risk management. (1)
- The agreements were set by a coordinating entity. (2)
- The agreements were set jointly. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLE9a Item 1 = Yes

RMLE9c [Forml] Were these informal agreements rather restrictive or rather helpful for your communication?

Rather restrictive 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Rather helpful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

FILTER IF RMLE9a Item 2 = Yes

RMLE9d [3C-FormI] Who set these specific formal guidelines?
[SC]

- The guidelines were set by either risk assessment or risk management. (1)
- The guidelines were set by a coordinating entity. (2)
- The guidelines were set jointly. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLE9a Item 2 = Yes

RMLE9e [FormI] Were these specific formal guidelines rather restrictive or rather helpful for your communication?

Rather restrictive 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Rather helpful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLE10a [Informal communication] During the last risk analysis, did you have informal communication with risk assessment?

The term "informal communication" refers to all communication between risk assessors and risk managers that takes place outside of the predetermined processes in risk analysis (e.g., a spontaneous phone call to clarify upcoming questions)

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

FILTER IF RMLE10a = 1

RMLE10b [Importance of informal communication] What impact did informal communication have in the last risk analysis process? [R]

	Do not agree at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Agree completely 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Informal communication facilitated open communication between risk assessment and risk management. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication improved understanding of the mandate to risk assessment. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication impaired the independence of the risk assessment process. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication improved the comprehensibility of the risk assessment. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication facilitated handing over the risk assessment to risk management. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informal communication increased trust between risk assessment and risk management. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLE11 [Mutual needs] Which of the following aspects did the last risk assessment report you received cover? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

- The results of the risk assessment. (1)
- Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate. (2)
- Uncertainties in the risk assessment. (3)
- Other limitations of the risk assessment. (4)
- Background information. (5)
- Raw data. (6)
- Details on the methodology. (7)
- Details on the impact of different management scenarios. (8)
- Recommendations for management strategies. (9)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLE12a [Common ground] To what extent did the last risk assessment report correspond to the question of risk management?

Not at all 1	2	3	4	Completely 5	I don't know / I prefer not to say 99
<input type="checkbox"/>					

Filter IF RMLE12a < 5

RMLE12b [Common ground] [MC, R] As far as you can tell from the last risk assessment report, why did the risk assessment not (fully) correspond to the question of risk management?

Please tick all that apply.		
Lack of data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Lack of specific information.	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Too many uncertainties in the data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Overly vague conclusions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Other (please specify): _____	<input type="checkbox"/>	88
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

RMLE13 [Common ground] How useful was the last risk assessment for your management decisions?

Not at all useful 1	2	3	4	Very useful 5	I don't know / I prefer not to say 99
<input type="checkbox"/>					

RMLE14 [Mutual needs] Which of the following aspects would you have liked to receive more information about in the final risk assessment report?

<i>Please tick all that apply.</i>		Code/ Filter [multiple choice]
The results of the risk assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate.	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Uncertainties in the risk assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Other limitations of the risk assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Background information.	<input type="checkbox"/>	5
Raw data.	<input type="checkbox"/>	6
Details on the methodology.	<input type="checkbox"/>	7
Details on the impact of different management scenarios.	<input type="checkbox"/>	8
Recommendations for management strategies.	<input type="checkbox"/>	9
Other (please specify): _____	<input type="checkbox"/>	88
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

RMLE15 [Understandability / common ground] How would you rate the comprehensibility of the last risk assessment report? [R]

If you saw several versions of the report (e.g., an earlier draft and the official version), please answer the question only in relation to the final version of the report.

	Do not agree at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Agree completely 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
The risk assessment report was written in an understandable way. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The risk assessment answered the exact question posed in the risk assessment mandate. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The conclusions from the risk assessment were difficult to follow. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had problems understanding how exactly the results of the risk assessment relate to the risk management mandate. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had difficulties understanding some of the technical terms used in the risk assessment. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLE16 [Comprehensibility / common ground] How could the comprehensibility of the last risk assessment report be improved?

<i>Please briefly specify below</i>		
<i>[open question]</i>		
I don't know / I prefer not to say	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

[RM] REFLECTION ON THE RISK ANALYSIS

In this part of the questionnaire, we would like you to take a step back and reflect on the last risk analysis that you were involved in as a whole.

RMLR1 [Quality of risk analysis process] How would you generally rate the quality of the following aspects within the last risk analysis process? [R]

	Very poor 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very good 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Work process. (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Transparency. (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Meeting risk analysis goals (effectiveness). (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Minimizing resource requirements (efficiency). (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Openness with risk assessment. (5)	<input type="radio"/>					
Flexibility. (6)	<input type="radio"/>					
Time management. (7)	<input type="radio"/>					
Timeliness. (8)	<input type="radio"/>					

RMLR2 [Satisfaction, dependent variable] How satisfied were you overall with the communication between you and the risk assessor during the last risk analysis?

Not at all satisfied 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very satisfied 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLR3a [Proximity, common ground] Had you worked previously with the particular risk assessor? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLR3a = 1

RMLR3b [Proximity / mutual needs] How important was it for your work in the last risk analysis process that you already knew the risk assessor who conducted the assessment for you?

Not at all important 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very important 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLR4 [Trust] How would you describe your relationship with the risk assessor in the last risk analysis? [R]

	Do not agree at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Agree completel y 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
We did not get to know each other personally while working on the risk analysis. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable about asking them all kinds of clarifying questions. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable about bringing up problems and challenges. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt comfortable about asking them for help. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I felt that my skills and expertise were valued by them. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trusted their abilities regarding the risk analysis process. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trusted them to work in line with my own interests. (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

RMLR5 [3C-Trust] Which role did trust play for the success of the last risk analysis? [SC, R]

- It was not necessary that risk assessors and risk managers trusted each other. (1)
- Trust was only necessary between supervisory staff of risk assessment and risk management, not on a working level. (2)
- It was crucial that all partners trusted each other. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLR6 [Mutual needs] On which aspects of the last risk assessment did you give some feedback? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

- The results of the risk assessment. (1)
- Risk benefit analysis (2)
- Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate. (3)
- Uncertainties in the risk assessment. (4)
- Other limitations of the risk assessment. (5)
- Background information. (6)
- Raw data. (7)
- Details on the methodology. (8)
- Details on the impact of different management scenarios. (9)
- Recommendations for management decisions. (10)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

RMLR7a[Information sharing] During the last risk analysis, did you feel any constraints in your communication with risk assessment? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RMLR7a = 1

RMLR7b [Information sharing] What kind of constraints were they?

Please specify below.

FILTER for [RA/RM]-Block (RA/RMCI1 to RA/RMCI5): BG1 = 1 OR BG1 = 3

End of Block: Questions on the last risk assessment/management

FILTER for Introduction [BOTH] and BLG1: IF BG1 = 2

[BOTH]_GENERAL QUESTIONS ON LAST RISK ANALYSIS

In this first part of the questionnaire, we would like to take a closer look at specific details within the risk analysis process. For this, we would like you to think about the **last risk analysis in which you were involved** that fulfils the following two criteria: 1) The risk assessment was requested via a mandate; i.e., via an official order or commission to perform a risk assessment. 2) The risk assessment has already been consulted for risk management purposes.

Please answer **all following questions** with this particular risk analysis in mind.

BLG1 [Organizational structure]

In this particular instance, did you... <i>Please note: The answer to this question is crucial for the remainder of the questionnaire, as it determines the questions that will be displayed for you. If you select "I don't know / I prefer not to say", you will not be able to continue with the survey.</i> [involvement in risk analysis]		Code/ Filter
... only provide the risk assessment, while the risk management was handled by someone else.	<input type="checkbox"/>	1 → [RA]-Blocks (skip introduction!)
... provide both risk assessment and risk management.	<input type="checkbox"/>	2 → BLG2
... only provide the risk management, while the risk assessment was handled by someone else.	<input type="checkbox"/>	3 → [RM]- Blocks (skip introduction!)
I don't know / I prefer not to say	<input type="checkbox"/>	99 → (Screenout)

BLG2 [Subject area] Within which subject area did you prepare the last risk analysis?
[MC]

- Biological hazards in food. (1)
- Chemical hazards in food. (2)
- Physical hazards in food. (3)
- Biological hazards in drinking water. (4)
- Chemical hazards in drinking water. (5)
- Biological hazards in feed. (6)
- Chemical hazards in feed. (7)
- Physical hazards in feed. (8)
- Biological hazards in water to animals. (9)
- Chemical hazards in water to animals. (10)
- Emerging risks (related to food or feed). (11)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

BLG3 [Routine vs. incident] Which of the following categories did your last risk analysis fall into? [SC]

- Routine risk assessment, i.e., a systematic review of all available scientific data to evaluate the magnitude of risks associated with certain hazards. (1)
- Rapid risk assessment, i.e., a risk analysis based on limited data due to time constraints (often used in initial stages of an event or after an incident of potential public health concern). (2)
- Expert opinion, i.e., a summary of evidence-based views given by experts in the field (often used when there is a lack of data). (3)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

BLG4 [Length of risk analysis] How long did the last risk analysis process take? [SC]

- Less than a month. (1)
- One to three months. (2)
- Four to six months. (3)
- Seven to twelve months. (4)
- More than a year. (5)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

BLG5 [Tasks and topics of work] Which tasks were you involved in during your last risk analysis? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

		Code/ Filter [multiple choice]
Screening and early warning.	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Problem framing.	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Determining how to assess the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Formulation of the mandate (i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment).	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Hazard identification.	<input type="checkbox"/>	5
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	6
Hazard characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	7
Risk characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	8
Gathering and assessing risk perceptions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	9
Gathering and assessing social concerns.	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
Compiling risk profiles.	<input type="checkbox"/>	12
Knowledge characterization (e.g. in terms of uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity).	<input type="checkbox"/>	13
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	14
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	15
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	16
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	17
Planning options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	18
Implementing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	19
Controlling the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	20
Evaluating the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	21
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
Risk communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>	23
Stakeholder engagement.	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

BLG6a [Opinion on separation] Would you have preferred that certain tasks of the last risk analysis process would have been performed by separate entities? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

Filter: IF BLG6a = 1

BLG6b Which of the following tasks should be performed separately?

Please tick all that apply.

		Code/ Filter [multiple choice]
Screening and early warning.	<input type="checkbox"/>	1

Problem framing.	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Determining how to assess the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Formulation of the mandate (i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment).	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Hazard identification.	<input type="checkbox"/>	5
Exposure and vulnerability assessment.	<input type="checkbox"/>	6
Hazard characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	7
Risk characterization.	<input type="checkbox"/>	8
Gathering and assessing risk perceptions.	<input type="checkbox"/>	9
Gathering and assessing social concerns.	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
Gathering and assessing socio-economic impacts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
Compiling risk profiles.	<input type="checkbox"/>	12
Knowledge characterization (e.g. in terms of uncertainty, complexity, ambiguity).	<input type="checkbox"/>	13
Judging the tolerability and acceptability of the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	14
Identifying / generating options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	15
Assessing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	16
Selecting options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	17
Planning options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	18
Implementing options to deal with the risk.	<input type="checkbox"/>	19
Controlling the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	20
Evaluating the implemented options.	<input type="checkbox"/>	21
Providing feedback on management practice to other risk analysis counterparts.	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
Risk communication.	<input type="checkbox"/>	23
Stakeholder engagement.	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
I don't know / I prefer not to say.	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

BLG7 [Organizational structure] Including yourself, how many people were involved in the last risk analysis?

If you don't know the exact number, please enter your best estimate.

_____ people

[@Joao: please program the text field so that the participants can only enter **numbers**, not letters.]

[BOTH] PREPERATION & EXECUTION OF THE RISK ANALYSIS

With the next questions, we want to learn more about how your latest risk analysis got started:

BLP1 [Formulation of mandate] How and by whom was the last risk assessment mandate formulated?

Please specify below

BLP2 What kind of information was included in the last risk assessment mandate?

Please tick all that apply.

- A description of the risk to be assessed. (1)
- The intended use of the risk assessment. (2)
- Information on different risk management strategies pertaining to this risk. (3)
- A description of the circumstance that gave rise to the enquiry. (4)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

BLP3a [MCDA] Did the last risk assessment mandate define the decision factors and criteria that would be used to compare different management options (for example specifications made for a multi criteria decision analysis, short MCDA)? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF BLP3a = 1

BLP3b [MCDA] What decision factors and criteria were these?

Please briefly specify below.

FILTER IF BLP3a = 1

BLP3c [MCDA] To what extent were these decision factors and criteria useful or not useful for the last risk analysis? [SC]

Not at all useful 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very useful 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

FILTER IF BLP3a = 1

BLP3d [MCDA] To what extent did these decision factors and criteria influence your last risk assessment? [SC, R – Except (3) & (99)]

- They influenced how the risk assessment was conducted. (1)
- They influenced how the results of the risk assessment were presented. (2)
- They did not influence the risk assessment. (3)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

BLP4 [Comprehensibility / common ground] How would you rate the comprehensibility of the last risk assessment mandate? [R]

If you saw several versions of the mandate (e.g., an earlier draft and the official version), please answer the question only in relation to the final version of the mandate.

	Do not agree at all 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Agree completely 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
The risk assessment mandate was written in an understandable way. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The mandate defined the risk to be assessed precisely and clearly. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The mandate clearly stated the purpose for which the assessment was needed. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had problems understanding what exactly was expected from my risk assessment. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I had difficulties understanding some of the technical terms used in the risk assessment mandate. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

[BOTH] REFLECTION ON THE RISK ANALYSIS

In this part of the questionnaire, we would like you to reflect on the last risk analysis in which you were involved as a whole.

BLR1 [Mutual needs] Which of the following aspects did your final risk analysis report cover? [MC]

Please tick all that apply.

- The results of the risk assessment. (1)
- Risk benefit analysis (2)
- Additional results not pertaining to the risk assessment mandate. (3)
- Uncertainties in the risk assessment. (4)
- Other limitations of the risk assessment. (5)
- Background information. (6)
- Raw data. (7)
- Details on the methodology. (8)
- Details on the impact of different management scenarios. (9)
- Recommendations for management decisions. (10)
- Other (please specify): (88) _____
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

BLR2 [Quality of risk analysis process] How would you generally rate the quality of the following aspects within the last risk analysis process? [R]

	Very poor 1 (1)	2 (2)	3 (3)	4 (4)	Very good 5 (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
Work process. (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
Transparency amongst all partners involved. (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
Meeting risk analysis goals (effectiveness). (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
Minimizing resource requirements. (efficiency) (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Openness. (5)	<input type="radio"/>					
Flexibility. (6)	<input type="radio"/>					
Time management. (7)	<input type="radio"/>					
Timeliness. (8)	<input type="radio"/>					

BLR3 [Frequency of joint provision] Generally speaking, how often do you provide both risk assessment and risk management during risk analysis processes?

Rarely

Always

I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)

[ALL] CHALLENGES AND IMPROVEMENTS

In this last section of the questionnaire, we want to take a look at a few general challenges you might encounter during the risk analysis and how they can be resolved. Additionally, we will focus on potential improvements of the risk analysis process. To answer the questions in this section, you can draw from all your experiences in risk analysis, not just the last risk analysis that you were involved in.

CI1 [Dealing with problems / challenges in the communication process] As in any process, communication challenges can arise within the risk analysis process. How often have you encountered the following challenges? [R]

	Never (1)	Rarely (2)	Sometimes (3)	Often (4)	Always (5)	I don't know / I prefer not to say (99)
If I couldn't reach my previous contact person, I didn't know who to approach. (1)	<input type="radio"/>					
If I needed additional expertise, I didn't know how to find the right person to talk to. (2)	<input type="radio"/>					
If I was absent at short notice (e.g., due to illness), there was no one who could answer questions about my work. (3)	<input type="radio"/>					
There was not enough time to resolve disagreements. (4)	<input type="radio"/>					
Procedural constraints hindered open communication with my risk analysis counterpart. (5)	<input type="radio"/>					

CI2a [Challenges encountered] Have you encountered any additional communication challenges? [SC]

- Yes (1)
- No (0)
- I don't know / I prefer not to say. (99)

FILTER IF RA/RMCI2a = 1

CI2b [Challenges encountered] What kind of communication challenges were they?

Please specify below.

FILTER IF RA/RMCI2a = 1

CI2c [Best practice] What approaches and strategies helped you in overcoming those different communication challenges?

Please specify below.

CI3 [Comprehensibility / common ground] The risk assessment mandate, i.e., the official order or commission to perform a risk assessment, shapes the entire subsequent risk analysis and can thus influence how well risk assessment and risk management perform. How do you think the formulation of the mandate could be improved to guarantee a successful risk analysis process?

Please specify below.

CI4 [Improvements] Is there anything else that you feel could improve the communication between risk assessment and risk management?

Please briefly specify below.

[ALL] BACKGROUND QUESTIONS II

Introduction **Before the end of this survey, we would like to ask you four short background questions for our statistics, which will give us a better overview of the participants in this survey.**

BG4 How many years of experience do you have in risk analysis?

___ year(s)

BG5 How old are you?

___ years

BG6 What is your gender? [SC]

- Male (1)
 - Female (2)
 - Non-binary (3)
 - I prefer not to say (99)
-

BG7 In what country do you work? [SC]

		Code/ Filter [single choice]
Albania	<input type="checkbox"/>	1
Austria	<input type="checkbox"/>	2
Belgium	<input type="checkbox"/>	3
Bosnia Herzegovina	<input type="checkbox"/>	4
Bulgaria	<input type="checkbox"/>	5
Croatia	<input type="checkbox"/>	6
Cyprus	<input type="checkbox"/>	7
Czech Republics	<input type="checkbox"/>	8
Denmark	<input type="checkbox"/>	9
Estonia	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
Finland	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
France	<input type="checkbox"/>	12
Germany	<input type="checkbox"/>	13
Greece	<input type="checkbox"/>	14
Hungary	<input type="checkbox"/>	15
Iceland	<input type="checkbox"/>	16
Ireland	<input type="checkbox"/>	17
Italy	<input type="checkbox"/>	18
Kosovo	<input type="checkbox"/>	19
Latvia	<input type="checkbox"/>	20
Liechtenstein	<input type="checkbox"/>	21
Lithuania	<input type="checkbox"/>	22
Luxembourg	<input type="checkbox"/>	23
Malta	<input type="checkbox"/>	24
Montenegro	<input type="checkbox"/>	25
Republic of North Macedonia	<input type="checkbox"/>	26
Netherlands	<input type="checkbox"/>	27

Norway	<input type="checkbox"/>	28
Poland	<input type="checkbox"/>	29
Portugal	<input type="checkbox"/>	30
Romania	<input type="checkbox"/>	31
Serbia	<input type="checkbox"/>	32
Slovakia	<input type="checkbox"/>	33
Slovenia	<input type="checkbox"/>	34
Spain	<input type="checkbox"/>	35
Sweden	<input type="checkbox"/>	36
Switzerland	<input type="checkbox"/>	37
Turkey	<input type="checkbox"/>	38
I don't know / I prefer not to say	<input type="checkbox"/>	99

[Thank you note]

Thank you for participating in this survey. Your answers are an important contribution to our end-goal of improving communication within the risk analysis process. We appreciate your time and effort in filling out the questionnaire. You can now exit the survey by closing this window.